

PERFORMANCE OF DIFFERENT SILKWORM HYBRIDS ON G-4 CULTIVAR OF MULBERRY.

Shingne A. R.* Rathod P. K., Undirwade D.B, Kadam P.S., Bandurkar K. V., Budhvat K.P.

Department of Entomology,

Post Graduate Institute, Dr P.D.K.V., Akola (MS), India

ashwinishingne2@gmail.com

MS Received: 07.03.2024; MS Revised:08.04.2025; MS Accepted:09.04.2025)

MS 3390

(RESEARCH PAPER IN ENTOMOLOGY,}

Abstract

The present investigation, titled "Performance of Different Silkworm Hybrids on the G-4 Cultivar of Mulberry," was conducted during the 2024-2025 period to examine the biological and economic traits of bivoltine silkworm hybrids on the G-4 mulberry variety. The experiment took place at the Sericulture Laboratory, Department of Entomology, Post Graduate Institute, Dr. PDKV Akola. It was designed as a Completely Randomized Design with seven treatments each replicated three times. Disease-free layings of silkworm hybrids, including FC₁×FC₂, FC₂×FC₁, TT₂₁×TT₅₆, TT₅₆×TT₂₁, S₈×CSR₁₆, SR₁₆×S₈, and SK₆×SK₇, were procured from the Central Sericultural Research and Training Institute in Mysore, Karnataka. These hybrids were tested against the G-4 mulberry variety in the present investigation. During the study, it was observed that among the seven hybrids used for rearing FC₁×FC₂ found superior over the rest of hybrids in case of single cocoon weight, single shell weight, shell ratio, filament length and filament weight. In contrast FC₂×FC₁ outperformed other hybrids in case of denier.

Keywords: *Bombyx mori* L., mulberry silk, Economic traits, Bivoltine hybrids, G-4 variety.

Introduction

The term "Sericulture" originates from the Greek word "sericos" meaning "silk" combined with the English word "culture" which refers to "rearing." Sericulture involves the rearing of silkworms for the production of raw silk. The silkworm, scientifically known as *Bombyx mori* L., is a lepidopteran insect that plays a significant role in the production of natural fibres (Bobade et al. 2019). Sericulture is the practice of raising silkworms in artificial or domesticated conditions and extracting raw silk from their cocoons. *Bombyx mori* is an important economic insect that transforms plant protein, particularly from mulberry into animal protein in the form of silk (Simi Simon et al. 2024). Mulberry plant is initial choice of mulberry silkworms. It is believed that mulberry plant is native of India or China particularly from lower slopes of Himalayas. (Tekule et al.2018). However, feeding an artificial diet also possible for silkworm. The natural silk is obtained from four species of silkworm viz. Mulberry silkworm (*Bombyx mori*), Tassar silkworm (*Antheraea mylitta*), Muga silkworm (*Antheraea assamensis*) and Eri silkworm (*Philosemia ricini*).Silk is an insect fibre known for its lustre, drape, and strength. Due to these unique characteristics, silk is often referred to as the "Queen of Textiles" around the world. India is home to one of the world's oldest civilizations and has made significant contributions to the global textile industry with silk being one of its most notable offerings. India ranks as the second-largest producer of silk globally and is also the largest consumer of this luxurious material. Furthermore, India is unique in that it produces all four commercial varieties of silk: Mulberry, Tassar (both Tropical and Oak), Muga, and Eri. The Indian sericulture industry is distinguished by its high employment potential, low capital requirements and ability to provide profitable income for silk growers (Anonymous, 2020). The sericulture industry provides livelihood opportunities for millions due to its high employment potential low capital requirements and profitable production processes. The industry primarily involves rural-based on-farm and off-farm activities generating significant employment. This potential has caught the attention of planners and policymakers, who recognize sericulture as a key avenue for the socio-economic development of India's largely agrarian economy (Anonymous, 2023).

Materials and methods

The experiment was conducted in rearing house at Sericulture Laboratory Department of Entomology, PGI, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola, during September 2024 to October 2024-25 to study the biology and economic traits of bivoltine silkworm hybrids on G-4 Variety of Mulberry. The experiment was conducted in Completely Randomized Design with seven treatments and three Replication. Following seven silkworm hybrid were selected for research trial viz. FC₁ X FC₂, FC₂ X FC₁, TT₅₆ X TT₂₁, TT₂₁ X TT₅₆, CSR₁₆ X S₈, S₈ X CSR₁₆, SK₆ X SK₇. The improved technology of silkworm rearing adapted in this present investigation was described by Krishnaswami (1978).

Observations were taken on following parameters on ten randomly selected larvae/ cocoons of silkworm hybrids from each replication of each treatment

Single cocoon weight: The cocoon weight will Recorded on 6th day of spinning. The average of 10 cocoons is taken as single cocoon weight.

Single shell weight: The cocoon will cut open at one end and shell weight will Recorded after removing pupae.

Cocoon shell Ratio (%)

$$\frac{\text{Single shell weight}}{\text{Single cocoon weight}} \times 100$$

Shell Ratio (%) = ----- x 100

Single cocoon weight

Cocoon filament length (m): Cocoon filament length was measured by reeling 10 cocoons in three Replication with the help of epprovate.

Denier - It is the term used to denote the thickness of silk filament and expressed in terms of ratio of weight of filament, to the filament length multiplied by 9000.

$$\frac{\text{Filament weight (g)}}{\text{Filament length (m)}} \times 9000$$

Denier = ----- x 9000

Filament length (m)

Result and discussion

This research aimed to assess the profound effects of feeding the highly regarded mulberry variety G-4 on the biology and economic traits of various silkworm hybrids. The compelling findings from this study are comprehensively presented in this research under the following information.

Single cocoon weight (g):

The bivoltine hybrid FC₁ X FC₂ exhibited the highest single cocoon weight at 1.91 grams, which was statistically similar to that of the hybrid TT₂₁ X TT₅₆ weighing 1.85 grams. Both hybrids were found to be superior to the others tested. The next best hybrid was FC₂ X FC₁ with a weight of 1.82 grams. The hybrids CSR₁₆ X S₈ (1.66 grams), S₈ X CSR₁₆ (1.61 grams), and SK₆ X SK₇ (1.51 grams) showed statistically comparable single cocoon weights. The lowest single cocoon weight was recorded for the hybrid TT₅₆ X TT₂₁ at 1.46 grams. Thore et al. (2023) also reported the Single Cocoon weight in hybrids FC₁ X FC₂ (1.92 grams). Additionally, Khaire (2023) reported the highest single cocoon weight for the same hybrid at 1.86 grams.

Single shell weight (g):

The hybrid FC₁ X FC₂ exhibited the highest single shell weight registering at 0.38 grams. It was closely followed by the hybrid FC₂ X FC₁ which had a weight of 0.36 grams and both were significantly better than the others. The second-best hybrid was SK₆ X SK₇ with a single shell weight of 0.32 grams this was statistically comparable to the hybrids CSR₁₆ X S₈ (0.31 grams), S₈ X CSR₁₆ (0.30 grams), and TT₅₆ X TT₂₁ (0.29 grams). The lowest single shell weight was recorded for the hybrid TT₂₁ X TT₅₆ at 0.29 grams. The results mentioned above align with the findings of Mele (2023), who recorded the weight of a single shell in the hybrid FC₁ X FC₂ at 0.40

grams. In addition, Pawar (2024) reported the weight of a single shell in the same hybrid as 0.38 grams.

Cocoon shell ratio (%):

The hybrid FC₁ X FC₂ exhibited the highest shell ratio at 20.16% which was statistically similar to the hybrids FC₂ X FC₁ (19.08%), TT₂₁ X TT₅₆ (19.05%), TT₅₆ X TT₂₁ (19.04%) and SK₆ × SK₇ (18.67%). The second-best hybrid CSR₁₆ X S₈, had a shell ratio of 18.48% which was statistically comparable to S₈ X CSR₁₆ which recorded a ratio of 17.07% and had the lowest cocoon shell ratio. Bobade et al. (2019) noted a shell ratio of 21.32% in the hybrid S₈ X CSR₁₆.

Filament length (m):

The hybrid FC₁ X FC₂ recorded the highest filament length measuring 981.13 m and was statistically similar to the hybrid FC₂ X FC₁ which had a filament length of 946.07 m. Both hybrids were superior to the other hybrids tested. The next best hybrid was S₈ X CSR₁₆ with a filament length of 924.78 m which was comparable to the hybrid TT₅₆ X TT₂₁ measuring 911.52 m. The hybrid TT₂₁ X TT₅₆ recorded a length of 863.00 m followed by the hybrid CSR₁₆ X S₈ at 838.43 m and the hybrid SK₆ × SK₇ which had the lowest filament length at 829.28 m. These findings regarding filament length are consistent with the observations of Mele (2023), who noted a filament length of 999.48 m for FC₁X FC₂.

Filament weight (g):

Observations on filament weight indicated that the highest filament weight was found in the hybrid FC₁ X FC₂ which weighed 0.33 grams.

Table 1: Performance of bivoltine silkworm hybrids on different economic traits

Treatments	Single cocoon wt (g)	Singleshell wt(g)	Shell ratio (%)	Filament length (m)	Filament wt (g)	Denier
FC ₁ × FC ₂	40.11	0.38	20.16	981.13	0.33	2.87
FC ₂ × FC ₁	39.47	0.36	19.08	946.07	0.29	3.16
TT ₅₆ X TT ₂₁	36.87	0.29	19.04	911.52	0.28	2.85
TT ₂₁ × TT ₅₆	36.80	0.29	19.05	863.00	0.30	2.83
CSR ₁₆ X S ₈	37.32	0.31	18.48	838.43	0.27	2.92
S ₈ X CSR ₁₆	37.33	0.30	17.07	924.78	0.23	2.73
SK ₆ × SK ₇	35.90	0.32	18.67	829.28	0.26	2.87
SE (m)±	0.02	0.03	0.31	12.36	0.02	0.13
CD at 5%	0.05	0.01	0.94	37.50	0.01	0.28

*-Significant at @5% level

References

1. **Anonymous.** Scenario of sericulture industry in Maharashtra State, India, Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies. 2016; 4(1):601-605. 3.
2. **Anonymous.** Annual report Central Silk Board, 2016 17. 4.
3. **BS Bobade, CB Latpate and RB Dake (2019).** Effect of feeding mulberry variety G-4 on economic traits of bivoltine silkworm (*Bombyx mori* L.) hybrids. Journal of Entomology and Zoology Studies 2019; 7(6): 289-291.
4. **KD Pawar, PK Rathod, KP Budhvat, PP Ubarhande, PR Puri (2024).** Studies of economic traits of different silkworm hybrids on V-1 cultivar of *morus alba*. 8(10):812-814.
5. **.Md. Ilyas, Vidhate GS, Ugale TB, Kamate GS et al.** performance of different bivoltine mulberry silkworm hybrids suitable for marathwada regions of India. Agric. Sci. Digest. 2012; 33(3):178-182, 201 DOI- 10.5958/j.0976-0547.33.3.003.
6. **Maske, S & Latpate, C & Matre, Y B. (2021).** Studies of the biology and economic traits of mulberry (*bombyx mori* l.) double csr hybrids on different mulberry variety.
7. **Maske, S & Latpate, C & Matre, Y B. (2022).** Studies of the Biology and Economic Traits of Mulberry (*Bombyx mori* L.) Double CSR Hybrids on Different Mulberry Variety. 2483-2489.
8. **Mele A. N. (2023)** Economic traits and biology of bivoltine silkworm hybrids on V-1 variety of *morus alba*, Dr. PDKV Akola, P85, (Unpublish thesis).

This was statistically comparable to the hybrids TT₂₁ X TT₅₆ which had a weight of 0.30 grams and FC₂ X FC₁ which weighed 0.29 grams. However, FC₁ X FC₂ was determined to be superior to all other hybrids tested. The next best hybrid was TT₅₆ X TT₂₁ weighing 0.28 grams which was statistically comparable to CSR₁₆ X S₈ (0.27 grams), SK₆ × SK₇ (0.26 grams) and S₈ X CSR₁₆ (0.23 grams). Similar results were reported by Mele (2023), who found a filament weight of 0.33 grams in hybrid FC₁ X FC₂.

Denier:

The highest denier value was observed in the hybrid FC₂ X FC₁ measuring 3.16. This value was statistically similar to the hybrids CSR₁₆ X S₈ (2.92) and FC₁ X FC₂ (2.87). The next best hybrid was SK₆ × SK₇ with a denier value of (2.87) and TT₂₁ X TT₅₆ (2.87) which was statistically comparable to TT₅₆ X TT₂₁ (2.85) and S₈ X CSR₁₆ (2.73) the latter showing the lowest denier value. These findings are consistent with the research by Thore et al. (2023), who reported a denier value of 2.61 for the hybrid FC₂ X FC₁.

Conclusion

Based on observations recorded on the weight of ten mature larvae (g), single cocoon weight (g), single shell weight (g), shell ratio (%), filament length (m), filament weight (g) and denier. Among the seven hybrids evaluated for rearing, FC₁XFC₂ exhibited the best results and it can be concluded that the bivoltine hybrid FC₁ X FC₂ reared on mulberry variety G-4 is the most suitable for rearing under Vidarbha conditions.

9. **Paighan P.D(2012)** Studies on performance of mulberry silkworm (*Bombyx mori* L.) hybrids under marathwada conditions.
10. **Sharma, Anita & Tripathi, N & Ayoub, Arshad. (2014).** Comparative analysis of developmental stages in six different bivoltine races of *bombyx mori*. International Journal of Recent Scientific Research. 5. 1969-1972.
11. **Sharma, Arti & Sharma, Palvi & Bandral, R S & Gupta, Rakesh & Bali, Kamlesh. (2023).** Influence of protein fortification on larval growth parameters of silkworm, *Bombyx mori* L. 2978-2982.
12. **Thore S., Chandrakant Latpate, Dhananjay Mohod, Shriram Shinde. (2023).** Studies on evaluation and identification of bivoltine silkworm hybrids (*Bombyx mori* L.). Pharma Innovation 12(5):918-922.
13. **Tekule, A. J., Latpate, C. B., Somwanshi, V. L., & Matre, Y. B. (2018).** Study on economic traits of bivoltine silkworm hybrids on V1 mulberry variety of *Morus alba*. International Journal of Chemical Studies, 6(5), 741-743.
14. **Vidhate JR.** Performance of some mulberry silkworm hybrids under Marathwada region. M.Sc. (Agri.) Thesis, MAU, Parbhani, 2003.
15. **Vidhate GS.** Evaluation of bivoltine mulberry silkworm (*Bombyx mori* L.) hybrids under Marathwada condition. M.Sc. (Agri.) Thesis, MKV, Parbhani. College of Agriculture, Raichur, 2009.